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D2.2 – BaTiO₃ Process Report

30/09/2024

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D2.2 BTO PROCESS REPORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report details the progress on development of a low-temperature atomic layer deposition (ALD) process for the functional ferroelectric BaTiO₃ (BTO), deliverable 2.2., which is crucial in the construction of electrooptical devices in WP4. For an ALD process of a ternary oxide, it is essential to be in control of binary end-systems, in this case TiO₂ and BaO (BaCO₃/Ba(OH)₂). Possible precursors for TiO₂ is already well-known in the community, thus the focus in precursor development was on exploring potential Ba-precursors. Parallel to this, ALD process development for a suitable low-temperature ozone-based TiO₂-process took place.

The precursors development approach is based on first principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations to screen possible Ba-precursors, making it possible to select relevant precursors for synthesis and further ALD process development. After screening, a selection of precursors was synthesized and tested with respect to applicable physical properties in the ALD-process. The precursors that passed both DFT and physical property tests were produced in larger batches and shipped to the ALD-facilities for process development.

An applicable TiO₂-process needs to have process parameters (temperature, chemistry) that matches the parameters of the developed BaO-process. Most importantly, the TiO₂-process cannot involve water as the oxygen source, as this will lead to formation of Ba(OH)₂ which will act as a water reservoir and render the ternary process uncontrolled. Very little has been reported on TiO₂-growth using alkoxides and ozone, but throughout this work we show that Ti-alkoxides and ozone lead to self-limiting ALD-growth under applicable conditions.

This new TiO₂-process is currently being combined with the process of the novel Ba-precursor, to study the compositional relationship during ALD-growth. At the time of this report, mixtures of the Ba- and Ti-processes are employed to reach the wanted stoichiometry in the resulting films.

In the way forward, studies on the crystallization of these mixtures to form epitaxial BTO will be carried out before the functionality of the crystalline films will take place.

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE REPORT

This report consists of three parts detailing the current status of the work of first principles calculations (chap. 2), precursors synthesis (chap. 3) and ALD-development (chap. 4), respectively. The output from these separate parts are then combined and commented in a scientific summary at the end of the report (chap. 5). Finally, chap. 6 presents future outlook and goals.

2 FIRST PRINCIPLES CALCULATION ON RELEVANT PRECURSORS

At Tyndall National Institute, first principles density functional (DFT) calculations in the gas phase have been performed for rapid screening of candidate Ba-precursors, providing feedback to our experimental precursor synthesis and deposition collaborators.

This allows a filtering approach to be pursued which has three steps to filter suitable Ba precursors from our initial list of metal precursors: precursor stability, gas-phase ligand exchange reaction, and precursor reaction on BTO surfaces.

In this period, we simulated with DFT gas phase models of target Ba precursors based on having Ba-O motifs in the molecule, which we name P1 and P2 for the two most tested precursors; the DFT studies allows us to test the stability of these precursors. We find that P1 and P2 are theoretically stable; comparison with the experimental synthesis work from Volatec shows that P2 is more viable as a precursor. We also found that P2 is more stable as a tetramer species.

Figure 1. Illustration of two target Ba precursors P1 (left) and P2 (right).

We have studied how the precursors P1 and P2 can be stabilised by adding an adduct, exploring triglyme and tetraglyme. The DFT calculations explore the stability and binding of the adducts at the precursors P1

and P2. We find that both triglyme and tetraglyme could stabilize P1 and P2, but triglyme have more negative formation energy than tetraglyme.

Figure 2. Illustration of two target Ba precursors P1 and P2 with triglyme (left) and tetraglyme (right).

Given the results from the analysis of the precursors, we moved to gas phase reaction of the precursor P2 with co-reactants used in the ALD process (ozone, O₃). We use ozone as the reactant and explore (1) how the O₃ molecule reacts at the precursor and (2) given that the reactive species is ¹O, how does this oxygen react with precursor ligands and insert into the ligand producing a series of products. This gives useful information regarding how the ligands can be removed in the Ba deposition.

Figure 3. Illustration of plausible by-products for gas-phase reactions between precursor P2 and ozone O₃.

These exothermic energies indicate that these are the plausible by-products during the ALD growth of BTO thin films using precursor P2 and co-reactant O₃. The selected precursor P2 is stable and results of gas-phase reactions indicate its potential for potential use in the ALD work at Oslo.

The successful Ba precursors are moving to the next step of detailed calculations of the ALD mechanism on BTO surfaces, working on low energy (001) Ti-O and Ba-O terminated surface models, which are ongoing and future tasks.

3 DEVELOPMENT OF PRECURSORS

Barium compounds were screened based on open literature and knowhow from the past, as well as supported by DFT calculation work at Tyndall. The selection to prepare four (4) barium compounds was made from 14 different alternatives. These barium compounds were prepared, and their properties were measured. Especially, the decomposition and vaporization behaviours of barium compounds were evaluated since it is important for atomic layer deposition (ALD). For that purpose, the Optical Diagnosis Instrument (ODIN) by Baldur Coatings unit was used.

Two barium compounds were chosen for further evaluations. Their storage stability is currently evaluated by long term stability tests. The deterioration of these compound occurs in days when stored at ambient temperatures in air. When stored under inert gas and in freezer, the thermal behaviour had not changed during 2 months. One compound is currently in the ALD tests at the University of Oslo.

Compound	Abbreviation	Thermal behaviour	Store
Ba-(Ligand not disclosed)	BaP1	Decomposes	
Ba-(Ligand not disclosed) with adduct	BaP1-A1	Unknown?	
Ba-(Ligand not disclosed)	BaP2	Vaporizes	in freezer > 1 month
Ba-(Ligand not disclosed) with adduct	BaP2-A1	Vaporizes after release of tetraglyme	in argon > 1 month, more data to be acquired

3.1 SYNTHESIS

While optimizing and designing synthetic pathways for the chosen precursors, emphasis was put on less hazardous starting materials, flexible/tunable reaction conditions, avoiding multistep reactions when possible and improve yields of the reaction.

In literature many barium precursors are mostly made using metallic barium, barium hydride or barium iodine, which are pyrophoric and/or sensitive for air & moisture, and expensive. Reactions are therefore often made in rigorous exclusion of air and moisture, which require extra steps in drying of each reagent and setting up the synthetic equipment. Yields of the reactions range from poor to decent but are often not high (> 80%). We chose to attempt reactions with barium nitrate and barium hydroxide as starting materials, as they are not air/moisture sensitive and more affordable. Syntheses were done in either anhydrous conditions using for example dried hydrocarbon solvents or in alcohol or alcohol/water mixture. For BaP1-A1 barium isopropoxide was used as starting material as (attempted) reaction pathway was different.

BaP1 was prepared from Ba(OH)₂ in 0-100% ethanol or methanol /water solution by adding ligand 1 and stirring for 1-24h at < 50 °C. Product precipitated, was filtered and dried.

BaP1-A1 was prepared by ligand exchange reaction in inert conditions. Barium isopropoxide was suspended in organic solvent containing equimolar amount of adduct 1. Ligand 1 was added dropwise and stirred for 24h. The product was filtered out and dried.

BaP2 was prepared from Ba(NO₃)₂ (note: could be done/tried from Ba(OH)₂ aswell, if wanted → (OH) incorporated in oligomer) in 25-100% ethanol or methanol /water solution. Ba(NO₃)₂ was suspended in solvent, protonated ligand 2 was added while stirring, and reaction was stirred for 0.5-72h at < 70 °C. Product was isolated by filtration, dried and purified. Yield up to 90%.

BaP2-A1 was prepared in inert conditions. BaP2 was dissolved in hydrocarbon solvent under N₂, stoichiometric amount or excess of adduct 1 was added and mixture was stirred for 2-48h. Solvent was removed and product dried. Yield 75~85%.

Studies show that barium precursors degrade over time. Storage conditions were studied (ongoing) and improved to have more viable delivery/usage for the prepared precursors. BaP2 is found to be stable/unchanged for 2 months in chosen storage conditions and BaP2-A1 for (at least) 2 weeks in ambient conditions.

3.2 ANALYSIS

Precursors were studied with ODIN-unit to have more understanding about their vaporization and decomposition. ODIN unit records visual changes over time and temperature. Range of temperature for

precursors prepared was 25-350 °C. Sublimation and condensation on reference plate, and any other visual changes such as melting or colour changes will be detected and analyzed (different colours on the graphs). Note that due to the design of the ODIN-unit, some events recorded might show elongated temperature range because condensation might happen either on the reference plate or the glass-cover of the unit, and re-evaporation from the glass cover is slow.

BaP1 showed no vaporization over the studied temperature range. Decomposition starts to occur at ~200 °C with gradual change of color from white to yellow and brown/black.

Figure 4: BaP1-A1 area of analysis (left, same used for all samples) and graph from the analysis (right). Minimal amount of vaporization after 200 °C which is not visible to eye on video.

BaP1-A1 in figure 4 behaved similarly as BaP1, minimal detection after 200 °C as decomposition started. However, after the measurement some white condensed, assumed to be BaP1 powder, was found on the inner walls of the glass-cover (not visible in video). Possible explanations could be only partial formation of BaP1 · A1, or limited vaporization of the said product.

Figure 5: Ba(L₂)₂ fresh sample (left) and aged sample (right).

In figure 5 we can see Ba(L₂)₂ melting around 195~220 °C followed by rapid evaporation of the precursor. Aged samples show various changes before the vaporization temperature of BaP2 and slow vaporization. The residue left on fresh samples is minimal where on aged samples the amount of residue increases.

Figure 6: Ba(L₂)₂ · A₁ ODIN-graph.

BaP2-A1 shows stepwise vaporization. Adduct A1 dissociates from the complex and evaporates around 100~140 °C. Curve is elongated in figure 6 because of A₁ condensation on the glass before camera. The BaP2 left shortly condenses into solid before sublimating/evaporating at around 220 °C.

In summary – BaP1 (with and without adduct) are considered to be the best options for further studies with ALD. These have been shipped to UiO for further studies in actual ALD-processes.

4 DEVELOPMENT OF THE ALD PROCESS(ES)

The development of a low-temperature ALD-process for epitaxial BaTiO₃ is one of the major outputs of the CONCEPT project. This section details the current status of development, broken down in sections for the constituent binary processes and the combination of these.

4.1 A VERSATILE PROCESS FOR TITANIUM DIOXIDE

One of two key binary constituents in a future BaTiO₃-process is a versatile process for TiO₂. The versatility pertains mainly to temperature, as the process at a later stage must be combined with the Ba-process(es) over a certain temperature range.

Processes for TiO₂ are well known, as TiO₂ finds applications within a wide variety of fields. Most commonly in modern materials technology is the use of *tetrakis(dimethylamino)titanium*, that readily reacts with either water or ammonia to form TiO₂ and TiN, respectively. Due to the possible incorporation of unknown amounts of nitrogen in the resulting films, especially when combined with other binary metal processes, the CONCEPT team wants to avoid the use of nitrogen-containing Ti-precursors.

Another well known Ti precursor candidate is TiCl₄, widely applied together with water to deposit TiO₂ with high purity and over a broad range of temperatures. This precursor is unfortunately not applicable for use in a final BTO-process, as highly stable BaCl₂ readily forms under typical ALD conditions.

A final possibility is a class of Ti alkoxides, that do not contain any contaminative elements and is based on a framework of Ti-O-bonds that in any case are needed in the final product. Within this class, titanium tetraisopropoxide (TTIP) is an interesting candidate. This precursor exhibits a medium growth per cycle when used with water, which offers the necessary stoichiometry control in the final ternary system. The isopropoxide is most commonly used together with water to form high quality TiO₂. In the BaTiO₃ process, however, water cannot be used as it will immediately lead to formation of stable Ba(OH)₂, which will also act as a water reservoir and hinder self-limiting growth. *I.e.*, the CONCEPT team studied the relatively rare combination of TTIP and O₃, and explored the versatility of that system.

As a first approach, the temperature stability was studied to investigate the temperature range at which TTIP + O₃ can be employed, while still resulting in self-limiting and uniform coating. Substrates were placed at different positions in the reaction chamber, and growth-per-cycle (GPC) was investigated by ellipsometry to shed light on uniformity (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Placement of substrates during growth for studying temperature range and uniformity.

Traditionally, ALD-processes have a “temperature window” of self-limiting growth where the GPC is constant or close to constant over a temperature range. This is not, however, *required* for a process to be ALD. The most important characteristic is saturative growth, *i.e.* growth that does not increase with increased pulse duration. This is exactly the case for the TTIP + O₃ system, which shows no clear ALD temperature window,

but still exhibits self-limiting growth over a range of temperatures (Figures 8 and 9). What becomes clear is that TTIP + O₃ can be used in the temperature range of 100 °C to 275 °C and still offer ALD. This makes the precursor combination a very good possible candidate for use together with Ba. No contaminative elements, wide temperature range of self-limiting growth, and applicable coreactant.

Figure 8: Temperature dependence of GPC for TTIP + O₃.

Figure 9: Example of self-limitation at 225 °C, showing stable GPC over a range of pulse times for TTIP. The point at 2000 ms TTIP pulse and 2000 deposition cycles is believed to be a fluked measurement due to thicker native oxide on the Si substrate wafer used.

The morphology of the TiO₂ films were studied to look for any crystallization behavior during deposition (Figure 10). This is something we would ideally like to avoid, since it can interfere with formation of BaTiO₃ at a later stage. On the other hand, phase and orientation control of TiO₂ over a wide temperature range is of importance towards other applications.

Figure 10: Morphology of TiO₂ thin films deposited over a wide temperature range.

We clearly observe a degree of crystallization starting at 200 °C, becoming dominant from 225 °C where the whole film is crystallized. Films at 225 °C, 250 °C and 300 °C were all found to adopt the rutile structure. While crystallization of the binary constituent is not ideal towards growth of BaTiO₃, we believe that the introduction of Ba will hinder the formation of TiO₂ grains to an extent where crystallites will not start to form.

In conclusion, TTIP + O₃ was found to constitute a very good option for further use in the deposition of BaTiO₃.

This work was presented at AVS-ALD2024 in Helsinki and is currently being written up to a scientific publication.

4.2 A PROCESS FOR BARIUM OXIDE/HYDROXIDE/CARBONATE

The second constituent for depositing BaTiO₃ is the binary process for BaO. This is a process that is much harder to control on its own, as the resulting BaO-films will immediately react with air or moisture to form Ba(OH)₂ and or BaCO₃. It is also possible that the use of a metalorganic precursor and O₃ will immediately form BaCO₃. This is not considered a problem, as this behavior will change when the precursor pair is used in a ternary system (known from work with Ca- and Sr-containing processes).

The most promising precursor (P2) developed from first principles calculations and synthetic precursor development was employed to understand its growth behavior under the wanted conditions.

Currently, this precursor, both P2 and P2-A1, is being tested for deposition at UiO. Preliminary results are promising, showing growth with a GPC of approx. 0.3 Å/cyc. A major issue is the long term stability of the precursor (refill from freezer needed for every run), but we believe that this challenge can be overcome by the addition of adducts.

Preliminary results also show that the major product using P2 with O₃ as the oxygen source is BaCO₃, that seems to be relatively stable in air. This is an expected result, as BaO is not very stable in CO₂-atmosphere and we expect formation of a significant amount of CO₂ upon reaction between the ligand and O₃. This is not seen as an issue going forward, as the Ti-O-Ba-containing intermediary species formed during ternary growth should not have the same affinity for carbonate formation.

4.3 THE TERNARY BTO PROCESS (OUTLOOK)

Per 30.09.2024, the BaO/BaCO₃- and TiO₂-processes are being combined in supercycles to get access to stoichiometry control in ternary films. This is ongoing work, and will be reported when results from x-ray fluorescence and x-ray diffraction measurements have taken place.

5 SUMMARY

The development of a low-temperature ALD-process for BaTiO₃ is *en route*. The combination of first principles calculations, precursor development and ALD-process development is going according to plan, and we are now exploiting these preliminary results to start depositing films of the ternary mixture.

Results from this WP have been presented at the AVS-ALD2024 conference in Helsinki (oral presentation by Ji Liu, poster by Dharshana P. Dinesh, poster by Jani Viljakka), and we currently expect at least three scientific

publications from this work. This excludes presentations and posters that will result from deposition of the ternary mixtures in the Ba-Ti-O system.